

Deliverable D1.1 Report on project management procedures and the establishment of the consortium bodies

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche
EC	European Commission
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
GA	Grant Agreement
GerBI	German BioImaging - Gesellschaft Fuer Mikroskopie Und Bildanalyse E.V.
GIDE	Global Image Data Ecosystem
MT	Management Team
SAC	Scientific Advisory Committee
UNSYD	The University of Sydney
UQ	The University of Queensland
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The foundingGIDE project aims to establish the foundation for a Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE), connecting various biological and biomedical image data resources worldwide to enable the sharing of metadata and data. GIDE will unite European research infrastructure and image data resource owners with their counterparts in Australia and Japan to create the groundwork for effective image data sharing. The foundingGIDE Project Management Plan details the strategy and a comprehensive project management infrastructure to allow for the effective implementation of the project.

1. Project Overview

The foundingGIDE project is funded by the Horizon Europe program under the HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions. The lump sum funding of 1.5 million euros is intended to lay the foundations of a Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE). It will facilitate data sharing across bioimage infrastructures in Europe, Japan and Australia Europe, and promote good practices for image data management across the globe. The project began in January 2024 and will continue until June 2026. The consortium consists of partners represented by 7 entities from 5 countries across 3 continents as tabulated below.

Consortium partners and country

Number	Short name	Full name	Country
1	Euro-Biolmaging	Euro-Biolmaging European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)	Finland
2	CNR	Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche	Italy
3	EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	Germany
4	GerBI	German Biolmaging	Germany
5	RIKEN	RIKEN - The Institute Of Physical And Chemical Research	Japan
6	UQ	The University of Queensland	Australia
7	UNSYD	The University of Sydney	Australia

The objectives of foundingGIDE project are as follows:

- Establish coordination among global open bioimage data resources
- Increase resource interoperability
- Engage with community initiatives and end-users
- Plan for sustainability
- Build an ecosystem for new resources to grow

2. Project Management Strategy

The foundingGIDE project coordinators at Euro-Biolmaging ERIC, scientifically supported by their Head of Image Data Services, are responsible for managing the successful implementation of the foundingGIDE project. The consortium bodies, described in detail in section 3, play a crucial role in the overall management of the project. The consortium consists of two internal bodies: the Management Team and the Steering Committee. There is one body which includes external members: the Scientific Advisory Committee.

The project consists of 12 Work Packages which are structured to meet the objectives outlined by the project.

The key activities of the project are built around 4 themes as listed below.

- Theme 1: **Global coordination** for data sharing among imaging infrastructures
- Theme 2: **Conserved ontologies** for effective cooperation
- Theme 3: **Enhanced interoperability** with harmonised metadata
- Theme 4: **Sustainable initiatives** by leveraging collaborations and developments

The 12 Work Packages for the project stem from the thematic topics and are structured to tackle specific objectives. The Work Package (WP) titles and corresponding WP leads are tabulated below.

WP	Title	WP Lead
1	Project management, dissemination and long-term sustainability	Euro-BioImaging
2	Global exchange on image data sharing and recommended ontologies	EMBL
3	Strengthening community coordination and Global Outreach	UQ
4	Recommendations on using existing biological imaging ontologies	CNR

5	Establishing shared ontologies	EMBL
6	Mapping and gap analysis for metadata harmonisation	RIKEN
7	Establish minimal shared interoperability metadata	EMBL
8	Mapping and gap analysis for preclinical metadata harmonisation	CNR
9	Engagement with technical communities driving bioimage standards	EMBL
10	Groundwork for metadata exchange between the BIA, IDR, SSB	GerBI
11	Data portal for search across imaging resources	EMBL
12	Interoperability across preclinical image dataset platforms	CNR

These WPs are interconnected, address specific aspects of the project, and fall under the thematic categories as follows.

3. Project Internal Communication and Procedures

Email

To enable easy communication within the project, all project partners can register themselves, to get access to various communication and project management tools provided for their benefit and to support efficient reporting. All registered participants of the project have been added to the foundingGIDE email list and project partners can use it to email all project partners if needed. All correspondence regarding the project can be made to the email foundingGIDE@eurobioimaging.eu which is also published on the website and social media channels.

Slack

All registered participants of the project have been added to the foundingGIDE Slack. This tool is being used for regular communication and project discussions where project members can be reached out individually or in groups. Separate channels have been created for discussion within WPs or thematic groups, and additional ones can be created on a needs basis.

Calendar

A calendar containing all the regular project meetings and events has been created and shared with the consortium members. All registered participants can view and make changes to events on the calendar using their google enabled account.

Project Meetings

The timeline for the Management Team meetings has been established and communicated to all the project partners. The meetings schedule with appropriate Zoom links and meeting rolling minutes have been added to the foundingGIDE calendar. The Management Team has nominated members for the Steering Committee (SC) and Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC). The frequency of these meetings has been agreed upon and has been detailed in the Section 4.

Project Document Storage

All project members are given access to a secure document storage system after they have registered to the consortium. Within the project folder all project partners have access to required project documents such as the grant agreement, partner contacts, reporting documentation, meeting presentations and minutes. All minutes of regular project and stream meetings are also maintained on a rolling basis.

4. Consortium Bodies

The project governance comprises of the following consortium bodies:

Coordinator

Euro-BioImaging ERIC is the legal entity which is acting as an intermediary to the beneficiaries and the European Commission (EC). It is in charge of overall coordination, monitoring of activities, management of scientific results, risk assessment, contingency planning, safeguarding the timely and accurate follow-up of the work plan, and financial management.

Within the foundingGIDE project, Euro-BioImaging ERIC is represented by the Euro-BioImaging Director General and a Project Manager. For all tasks related to scientific activities the Coordinator is supported by the Euro-BioImaging's Head of Image Data Services, and WP and Task leads. Regarding organisational, administrative and EC related tasks the coordinator is supported by the Project Manager who is responsible for internal communication, meeting organisation, and day-to-day project management.

Steering Committee

The Steering Committee is the decision making body for the project and it consists of up to two representatives from each beneficiary with the Euro-BioImaging Director General as chair. The Steering Committee will meet at least once a year and extraordinary meetings can be set up at any time upon request of the Scientific Advisory Committee or one third of the Members of the Steering Committee.

Members of the Steering Committee

Name of Member	Role	Partner
John Eriksson	Coordinator, SC Chair, WP 1 Lead	Euro-BioImaging
Sudeep Das	Coordinator, Project Manager	Euro-BioImaging
Aastha Mathur	Scientific Coordinator	Euro-BioImaging
Dario Longo	WP 4,8,12 Lead	CNR
Linda Chaabane	WP 4,8,12 Advisor	CNR
Matthew Hartley	WP 5,7,11 Lead	EMBL
Antje Keppler	WP 2,9 Advisor	EMBL
Josh Moore	WP 10 Lead	GerBI
Stefanie Weidtkamp-Peters	WP 10 Advisor	GerBI
Shuichi Onami	WP 6 Lead	RIKEN
Aiko Sekiguchi	WP 6 Support	RIKEN
Wojtek Goscinski	WP 3 Lead	UQ
Peter Bugeia	WP 3 Lead	UQ
Ryan Sullivan	WP 4,8,12 Contributor	UNSYD
David Poger	WP 3, 6, 9 Contributor	UNSYD

Management Team

The Management Team comprises of the Work Package leads and Task leads, the Project Manager and Euro-BioImaging's Head of Image Data Services as Chair. The team will monitor and assess the critical risks associated with the project and implement mitigation measures as required. It will develop internal procedures for the review of deliverables. It will also plan progress assessment at suitable times to monitor the project progress at a WP level. The team has decided to meet every 4th Thursday of the month and will discuss the implementation of the project objectives and report progress. These meetings will converge discussions from different WPs and project working areas.

Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC)

The individuals on the SAC are nominated by the Management Team. They will be strategically selected to strengthen the global community and help drive the objectives of foundingGIDE. The decision to select a nominee to become a SAC member will be taken by the Steering Committee. At least half of the SAC members shall be fully independent and external from the Consortium. The SAC will act as the advisory body for the execution of the project, oversee project progress and provide

advisory support to the Steering Committee. The SAC shall meet at least once a year and extraordinary meetings can be set up at any time at the request of the Steering Committee or 1/3 of the members of the Management Team.

5. Project Timeline

As a part of the project management procedure, a timeline for the meetings of each of the consortium bodies and the due dates for all the deliverables and milestones has been established.

2024					
M1	January 2024				
M1	18-Jan-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M2	February 2024				
M2	15,16-Feb 24	Virtual Kick-off meeting	All Work Package presentations, External presentations & discussions	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M3	March 2024				
M3	28-Mar-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M4	April 2024				
M4	25-Apr-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M5	May 2024				
M5	23-May-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M6	June 2024				
M6	27-Jun-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M6	30-Jun-24	Milestone 1	Project webpage	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M6	30-Jun-24	Deliverable 1.1	Report on project management procedures and the establishment of the consortium bodies	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M6	30-Jun-24	Deliverable 1.2	Data Management Plan	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M6	30-Jun-24	Deliverable 1.3	Communication and Outreach strategy plan	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M7	July 2024				
M7	25-Jul-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M8	August 2024				
M8	22-Aug-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M9	September 2024				
M9	26-Sep-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M10	October 2024				
M10	24-Oct-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging

M11	November 2024			
M11	28-11-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M12	December 2024			
M12	19-12-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
2025				
M13	January 2025			
M13	23-Jan-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M14	February 2025			
M14	27-Feb-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M15	March 2025			
M15	27-Mar-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M16	April 2025			
M16	24-Apr-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M17	May 2025			
M17	22-May-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M18	June 2025			
M18	26-Jun-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M18	30-Jun-25	Milestone 2	First GIDE developer event held	WP2 EMBL
M18	30-Jun-25	Milestone 3	First GIDE coordination event held	WP2 EMBL
M18	30-Jun-25	Milestone 4	Common meeting with global imaging communities	WP3 EMBL
M18	30-Jun-25	Deliverable 1.5	Policy Brief M18	WP1 EMBL
M18	30-Jun-25	Deliverable 2.1	Landscape analysis of existing ontologies and recommendations on a set of imaging ontologies	WP2 EMBL
M18	30-Jun-25	Deliverable 4.1	Report on the recommended ontologies for preclinical image datasets and technologies	WP4 CNR
M18	30-Jun-25	Deliverable 6.1	Report in metadata model overlap and gaps	WP6 RIKEN
M18	30-Jun-25	Deliverable 9.1	Report on external GIDE network engagement	WP9 EMBL
M19	July 2025			
M19	24-Jun-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M20	August 2025			
M20	28-Aug-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1 Euro-Biolmaging
M21	September 2025			

M21	25-Sep-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M21	TBD	Project Review	First Project Review	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M22	October 2025				
M22	23-Oct-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M23	November 2025				
M23	27-Nov-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M24	December 2025				
M24	18-Dec-25	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
2026					
M25	January 2026				
M25	22-Jan-26	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M26	February 2026				
M26	26-Feb-26	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M27	March 2026				
M27	26-Mar-24	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M28	April 2026				
M28	23-Apr-26	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M29	May 2026				
M29	28-May-26	MT meeting	Management Team meeting	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M30	June 2026				
M30	TBD	Project Review	Second Project Review	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M30	30-Jun-26	Milestone 5	GIDE community event in Australia	WP3	UQ
M30	30-Jun-26	Milestone 6	GIDE community event in Japan	WP3	RIKEN
M30	30-Jun-26	Milestone 7	Publication of exchangeable metadata	WP10	GerBI
M30	30-Jun-26	Milestone 8	Catalogue indexing pipeline	WP11	EMBL
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 1.4	Sustainability strategy	WP1	EMBL
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 1.6	Policy Brief M30	WP1	EMBL
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 1.7	New ontologies implemented on the Euro-Biolmaging Web Portal and Web Portal linked to image data in public repositories	WP1	Euro-Biolmaging
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 3.1	Engagement with GIDE	WP3	EMBL
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 5.1	Updating existing ontologies, and implementing in data resources	WP5	EMBL
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 5.2	Maintenance plan for ontology sustainability	WP5	EMBL

M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 7.1	Minimal shared interoperability metadata set	WP7	EMBL
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 8.1	Recommended harmonised metadata model for preclinical image datasets	WP8	CNR
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 10.1	Model description and snapshot	WP10	GerBI
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 11.1	Data portal and supporting API	WP11	EMBL
M30	30-Jun-26	Deliverable 12.1	Tools for ontology and metadata management, and metadata interoperability	WP12	CNR

6. Conclusion

The foundingGIDE project management plan describes the project management strategy, the foundingGIDE consortium bodies and the project timeline. The project management strategy is designed to be responsive and adaptive to the needs of the project, and can be updated over the course of the project to promote internal and external communication and coordination of activities. The structured project management plan will allow for the successful implementation of the foundingGIDE project.

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